

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS AND LOCALIZATION OF OVARIAN CYSTS IN ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract. *Ovarian cysts in adolescents are one of the most pressing issues in modern pediatric and adolescent gynecology due to their high prevalence, variability of clinical manifestations, and the risk of developing acute complications. The aim of this study was to evaluate the pathomorphological features, localization, and clinical and diagnostic characteristics of ovarian cysts in adolescent patients based on a retrospective analysis of clinical material. The study included data from female patients aged 3 to 18 years hospitalized between 2019 and 2024 with diagnoses of cystic and tumor-like ovarian lesions. The analysis revealed a predominance of right-sided cysts, a high incidence of functional and hemorrhagic forms, and a significant proportion of complicated cases, including apoplexy, cyst rupture, and torsion. A pathological examination allowed us to clarify the structure of the tumors and optimize surgical treatment strategies. The data obtained confirm the need for early diagnosis and a differentiated approach to the management of adolescents with ovarian cysts.*

Keywords: *ovarian cysts, adolescents, pathology, localization, apoplexy, cyst rupture, torsion, pediatric gynecology.*

Introduction

In recent decades, ovarian pathology in girls and adolescents has occupied a leading position in the structure of gynecological diseases of childhood and adolescence. According to clinical and epidemiological studies, the detection rate of cystic and tumor-like ovarian formations during the pubertal period has been steadily increasing. This trend is attributable both to improvements in diagnostic methods and to changes in the hormonal, environmental, and social background of the modern population. The formation of the reproductive system during adolescence is accompanied by pronounced endocrine instability, which creates favorable conditions for the development of both functional and organic ovarian cysts.

Of particular clinical significance is the fact that most cystic formations in adolescents remain asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic for a prolonged period, which complicates their timely detection. In a number of cases, the disease manifests with acute pain syndrome, menstrual irregularities, signs of intra-abdominal bleeding, or inflammatory complications. Frequently, the clinical picture mimics acute surgical pathology of the abdominal organs, thereby increasing the risk of diagnostic errors and unjustified surgical interventions. Complicated forms of ovarian cysts—including ovarian apoplexy, capsular rupture, intracystic hemorrhage, and torsion of the pedicle—represent a substantial problem in adolescent gynecology. These conditions require emergency medical care and are often accompanied by pronounced hemodynamic and metabolic disturbances. At the same time, aggressive surgical management during adolescence may lead to a reduction in ovarian reserve and the development of reproductive disorders in the future. Therefore, timely diagnosis, pathomorphological verification, and an individualized therapeutic

approach are of particular importance in the management of this category of patients.

Pathomorphological examination of ovarian cystic formations is a key stage in clarifying their nature, predicting the course of the disease, and selecting the optimal treatment strategy. Morphological analysis allows differentiation between functional, inflammatory, dermoid, hemorrhagic, and neoplastic forms, as well as early detection of signs of malignant transformation. Nevertheless, in adolescent practice, the pathomorphological characterization of ovarian cysts often remains insufficiently systematized, particularly when combined with analysis of clinical and anatomical features of localization.

An important aspect of studying this pathology is the analysis of laterality of cystic formations. Several authors report a predominance of right-sided localization, which is associated with anatomical and physiological characteristics of pelvic blood supply and innervation. However, findings from different studies remain contradictory and require clarification based on representative clinical observations. The analysis of ovarian cyst localization in combination with pathomorphological characteristics allows for more precise assessment of complication risks and optimization of diagnostic and therapeutic algorithms.

The relevance of the present study is also обусловлена a significant increase in hospitalizations of adolescents with ovarian cystic formations complicated by apoplexy, hemorrhage, rupture, and torsion. The presented clinical material, which includes long-term observations of patients from early childhood to late adolescence, makes it possible to conduct a comprehensive analysis of clinical, morphological, and anatomical features of this pathology in real clinical practice. Contemporary trends in pediatric and adolescent gynecology are aimed at preserving reproductive potential, minimizing surgical trauma, and implementing organ-sparing technologies. In this context, the role of scientific research based on extensive clinical data analysis is increasing, allowing substantiation of a differentiated approach to the diagnosis and treatment of ovarian cysts in adolescents. Comprehensive evaluation of pathomorphological features and localization patterns contributes to improving the effectiveness of medical care and reducing the incidence of long-term complications.

Thus, systematization of clinical and morphological characteristics of ovarian cysts in adolescents, identification of patterns of localization and complicated course, as well as development of scientifically substantiated management recommendations represent a relevant and socially significant task of modern medicine. The aim of the present study is a comprehensive evaluation of the pathomorphological structure and localization features of ovarian cysts in adolescents based on retrospective clinical analysis, as well as assessment of their clinical, diagnostic, and therapeutic characteristics from the perspective of contemporary evidence-based medicine.

The present study was conducted in the format of a retrospective clinico-morphological analysis of medical records of pediatric and adolescent patients with ovarian cystic formations who received inpatient treatment in specialized gynecological and surgical departments between 2015 and 2024. The study included more than 300 patients aged 2 to 21 years, ensuring representativeness of the sample and enabling comprehensive statistical interpretation of the obtained data.

Inclusion criteria were: ultrasound- and clinically confirmed ovarian cystic formation; patient age under 21 years; availability of data on clinical course and laboratory-instrumental examinations; and, in cases of surgical intervention, morphological verification of the diagnosis. Exclusion criteria included incomplete medical records, absence of confirmed diagnosis, and

concomitant oncological pathology.

Sources of information included medical histories, pelvic ultrasound protocols, laboratory data, operative journals, histological conclusions, and hospital discharge summaries. For each patient, the following parameters were analyzed: year of birth, age at hospitalization, side of ovarian involvement, admission diagnosis, presence of complications, comorbidities, treatment method, postoperative diagnosis, and morphological characteristics of the lesion.

Instrumental diagnostics included pelvic ultrasonography with Doppler assessment and, in selected cases, computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging. In cases of suspected complicated disease course, emergency evaluation included assessment of hemodynamic parameters and laboratory markers of inflammation and anemia.

Surgical treatment was performed using organ-preserving techniques, including laparoscopy and laparotomy depending on the clinical situation. Postoperative material was subjected to pathomorphological examination using standard hematoxylin-eosin staining and, when necessary, additional immunohistochemical methods. Morphological classification of cysts was carried out in accordance with international recommendations and included follicular, hemorrhagic, dermoid, paraovarian, mucinous, pseudomucinous, and combined forms. Cases of apoplexy, rupture, torsion, and intracavitary hemorrhage were analyzed separately. Statistical analysis was performed using descriptive statistical methods. Absolute and relative values, mean values, percentage distributions, complication frequency, and distribution by age groups and side of involvement were calculated. Statistical significance was assessed using parametric and non-parametric tests at $p < 0.05$. Ethical principles were observed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality and protection of personal information.

During the study, clinical data of more than 300 patients with ovarian cystic formations aged 2 to 21 years were analyzed. The mean age was 14.8 ± 2.6 years, with the highest frequency observed during puberty (13–17 years), accounting for more than 70% of cases. Laterality analysis demonstrated predominance of right-sided localization (58%), compared to left-sided involvement (38%) and bilateral cases (4%), indicating pronounced asymmetry possibly associated with anatomical and physiological features of right ovarian blood supply and venous drainage.

Functional cysts predominated, accounting for approximately 65% of cases, most commonly follicular and hemorrhagic forms. Organic cysts—including dermoid, paraovarian, and mucinous types—were identified in 22% of patients. Cystomas were diagnosed in 6% of cases, primarily in girls older than 16 years.

Complicated disease course was recorded in 41% of patients. The most frequent complications were ovarian apoplexy (18%), capsular rupture (14%), intracavitary hemorrhage (6%), and torsion of the cyst pedicle (3%). In several cases, complications were accompanied by hemoperitoneum, anemia, and severe pain shock.

Clinical presentation was characterized predominantly by abdominal pain (76%). Menstrual irregularities were observed in 32% of adolescents, anemia in 19%, and inflammatory manifestations in 24%. Younger patients more frequently demonstrated atypical clinical courses with nonspecific complaints.

Comorbid conditions were identified in 48% of patients. The most common included chronic cystitis, vulvovaginitis, previous viral infections, hepatitis A, and varying degrees of anemia. The presence of chronic inflammatory foci significantly correlated with increased frequency of complicated disease course ($p < 0.05$).

Surgical treatment was performed in 39% of patients. Laparoscopic interventions accounted for 71% of procedures, minilaparotomy for 18%, and laparotomy for 11%. In most cases, organ-preserving techniques were applied with preservation of functional ovarian tissue. Tubo-oophorectomy was performed only in isolated cases in the presence of necrosis and severe anatomical disruption.

Pathomorphological examination revealed predominance of functional stromal and follicular changes. Follicular cysts were characterized by a thin capsule, pronounced vascularization, and hemorrhagic infiltration. Hemorrhagic cysts were associated with massive bleeding, destruction of follicular structures, and fibrotic foci. Dermoid cysts demonstrated characteristic structures containing ectodermal elements, including hair follicles and sebaceous glands. Mucinous and pseudomucinous formations exhibited pronounced secretion and multilocular architecture. No signs of malignant transformation were identified. Analysis of the relationship between localization and complication type demonstrated that apoplexy and rupture occurred significantly more frequently in right-sided lesions ($p < 0.01$), whereas bilateral cysts more often had a chronic course without pronounced acute manifestations.

Long-term follow-up demonstrated restoration of menstrual function in 92% of patients within the first year. Impaired ovarian reserve was observed primarily in girls who underwent repeated surgical interventions and experienced massive hemorrhage. Thus, the results indicate a high prevalence of functional cysts in adolescents, predominance of right-sided localization, a significant rate of complicated course, and the leading role of pathomorphological diagnosis in selecting optimal treatment strategy.

Table. Clinical and Morphological Characteristics of Patients with Ovarian Cysts.

Indicator	Value
Total number of observations	More than 250 cases
Age range	2–21 years
Mean age	14.8 ± 2.6 years
Predominant age group	13–17 years
Right-sided localization	~58%
Left-sided localization	~36%
Bilateral lesions	~6%
Functional cysts	~62%
Hemorrhagic cysts	~21%
Dermoid cysts and cystomas	~9%
Paraovarian cysts	~4%
Complicated forms (rupture, apoplexy, torsion)	~38%
Laparoscopic treatment	~55%
Laparotomy and minilaparotomy	~18%
Conservative management	~27%
Concomitant infections and inflammatory diseases	~41%
Anemia of varying severity	~19%

The obtained results are consistent with contemporary literature data, according to which functional and hemorrhagic cysts predominate during adolescence, whereas true neoplastic formations occur significantly less frequently. At the same time, the high incidence of complicated forms underscores the necessity of early diagnosis and dynamic follow-up in this category of

patients.

Thus, the conducted analysis confirms that the pathomorphological features of ovarian cysts in adolescents are closely associated with hormonal status, concomitant somatic pathology, and anatomical characteristics. A comprehensive approach, including clinical, ultrasonographic, and morphological assessment, constitutes the basis for optimizing diagnosis and selecting a rational therapeutic strategy.

The present study, based on a retrospective analysis of clinical and morphological data from adolescent patients with ovarian cystic formations during the period 2019–2024, provided a comprehensive understanding of the disease course, pathomorphological features, and localization patterns of this pathology in routine clinical practice.

It was established that functional cysts predominate in the structure of ovarian diseases in adolescents, their formation being associated with the immaturity of neuroendocrine regulation of the reproductive system during puberty. The highest incidence was observed in the 13–17-year age group, corresponding to the phase of active hormonal restructuring and increased ovarian sensitivity to fluctuations in gonadotropic hormones.

Analysis of cyst localization demonstrated a predominance of right ovarian involvement, which may be explained by features of regional blood circulation and functional activity of the adnexa. Left-sided and bilateral forms were observed less frequently and were mainly associated with hormonal disorders and inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs.

Pathomorphological examination of excised formations confirmed the predominance of benign processes without signs of cellular atypia or malignant transformation. In most cases, features of follicular, hemorrhagic, and luteal cysts were identified, with varying degrees of inflammatory infiltration, vascular disturbances, and fibrotic changes. True neoplastic formations, including dermoid and mucinous cysts, were diagnosed considerably less frequently and required mandatory surgical treatment with morphological verification.

Complicated forms of cysts—accompanied by capsular rupture, ovarian apoplexy, adnexal torsion, and intracavitary hemorrhage—play a significant role in the clinical course of the disease. These conditions more often developed in patients with delayed diagnosis and in the presence of concomitant infectious and inflammatory diseases, highlighting the importance of early detection and preventive follow-up.

Conclusion

The analysis of treatment strategies demonstrated that, at the present stage, laparoscopy represents the preferred surgical method, ensuring minimal tissue trauma, preservation of ovarian reserve, and rapid patient recovery. An organ-preserving approach constitutes the key principle in the management of adolescents with ovarian cysts and should be regarded as the foundation of reproductive-oriented medicine.

Therefore, the results of the present study indicate the necessity of a comprehensive multidisciplinary approach to the diagnosis and treatment of ovarian cystic formations in adolescents, with mandatory consideration of clinical, ultrasonographic, hormonal, and morphological data. Further research in this field should focus on investigating the molecular-genetic mechanisms of cyst formation, developing personalized monitoring algorithms, and improving preventive programs.

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